

CULTiVATE

DMP: Data Management V1

D1.2: Data Management Plan V1
WP 1, T 1.4

Authors: Alwynne McGeever (TCD); Anna Davies (TCD)

Updated plan (V2) due in December 2024

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Technical references

Project Acronym	CULTIVATE
Project Title	CULTIVATE: Co-Designing Food Sharing Innovation for Resilience
Project Coordinator	Trinity College Dublin Anna Davies daviesa@tcd.ie
Project Duration	January 2023 – January 2026 (48 months)
Deliverable No.	D1.2
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 1 – Project Management
Task	T1.4 – Data Management
Lead beneficiary	1 (TCD)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	7 (UB)
Due date of deliverable	31 June 2023
Actual submission date	30 May 2023

*PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project’s page)

SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1.1	30.05.23	TCD	Alwynne McGeever, Anna Davies

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Table 1: Glossary of key terms

Term	Definition
CULTIVATE Data Types:	
Non-shareable data	Data that will not be made available. The eligible criteria are Privacy; Intellectual Property and/ or jeopardising the project's main objectives. These include the project deliverables with a 'SEN' status
Metadata	data describing restricted access data, shareable data and research outputs, according to the standardised fields specified in Table 2. Metadata will be deposited on the Zenodo repository, under a CC0 usage license, and remain available for at least five years after the project ends
Restricted access data	raw data generated by research and innovation activities. These data will not be deposited on Zenodo, and needs to be requested by contacting the data author. Metadata on Zenodo for these data will include details on how to request the data from the data author
Shareable data	raw data generated by research and innovation activities that will be made openly available on Zenodo, and additional appropriate repositories, according to FAIR principles. Sharing of shareable data may be subject to embargos relating to publication of research outputs. All shareable data will be licensed as Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY)
Research outputs	data generated by research and innovation activities that has undergone processing, analysis, critical review and presented in an accessible open access format designed for target groups. Research outputs include project deliverables with a 'PU' status, reports, policy briefs, interactive online tools, AIRTABLE spreadsheets, peer reviewed literature, video presentations, summary graphics, public project deliverables and other accessible forms of documents and media. All research outputs created by CULTIVATE will be made freely available on the project website and shared on relevant platforms such as MUFPP and GAIN's Food Action Cities platform and the EU Food Loss and Food Waste resources platform. In addition to publication on the project website, PU project deliverables will be available on CORDIS and metadata for all research outputs will be deposited on Zenodo. All research outputs will be licensed for free use, under a Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY)
AIRTABLE	A cloud based service as a spreadsheet-database hybrid, with the features of a database but applied to a spreadsheet

Cas	Cascoland
Dublin Core Metadata	a set of fifteen main metadata items for describing digital or physical resources
FAIR	guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
Microsoft SharePoint	A Microsoft 365 app that provides an online document management system, with a secure place to store, organize, share, and access information from any device
Microsoft Teams	A Microsoft 365 app for business communication and collaboration with chat channels, video call functionality and full integration with other Microsoft 365 apps, such as SharePoint
OpenAIRE	an open Scholarly Communication Infrastructure that create and operate services for Open Science
UB	Universitat de Barcelona
ULUND	Lund University
Utr	Utrecht Municipality
WUR	Wageningen University
Zenodo	A general-purpose repository, developed by OpenAIRE, to share open and FAIR research outputs

1. Project Summary

CULTIVATE uses a multi-actor approach to build sustainability and resilience in urban and peri-urban areas through a ground-breaking online social innovation support platform – The Food Sharing Compass. Built with and for five key stakeholder groups – food sharing initiatives, policy makers, food supply actors, researchers, and citizens – the platform will make it possible to navigate diverse food sharing landscapes and cultures, in order to understand, develop, replicate, expand and strengthen sustainable food sharing in Europe, supporting the European Green Deal’s Action Plan, Food 2030, the Farm to Fork Strategy and the EU’s climate change ambitions. The open access Food Sharing Compass will comprise five innovative tools:

1. The SHARECITY200 Database: an interactive automated mapping, tracking and monitoring database of food sharing initiatives that will add more than 100 new locations to the SHARECITY100 Database;
2. The Food Sharing Calculator: which enables comprehensive and holistic assessment of the costs, benefits and impacts of food sharing for all stakeholders;
3. The Menu of Good Governance: which provides options for developing policy making which facilitates sustainable food sharing;
4. The Library of Citizen Engagement: which supports establishing, expanding and maintaining inclusive participation in sustainable food sharing;
5. The sustainable food sharing Community of Practice: which will be established through a bespoke Amplification Programme to optimise the potential for mutual learning and exploitation of the Food Sharing Compass well beyond the project.

In essence, CULTIVATE will establish the EU as the global frontrunner in the development of resilient and inclusive food sharing economies, identifying drivers and implementation gaps and challenging existing theories and practices which currently constrain sustainable food sharing.

2. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

CULTIVATE will re-use and build on existing data and methods developed during the SHARECITY project: a) it will add another 100 UPU locations in EU MS /AC to the 100 locations (including 25 locations in the EU) already contained within the SHARECITY100 Database, automating search functions to do this and integrating new and old data into the SHARECITY200 Database (WP2); b) it will integrate SHARECITY's SHARE IT web app, which will be upgraded with an ERC PoC project led by CULTIVATE's PI, into the Food Sharing Calculator (WP3) (Table 2).

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

CULTIVATE will collect and/or generate data through literature reviews, web scraping, workshops, interviews, surveys, social media crowd sourcing, virtual and face to face citizen science activities, observation, and fieldwork. This will generate the raw data in the format of audio-visual data (recordings, images), text (transcripts, primary documents, deliberation, and observation notes) and tabular spreadsheet data (e.g. survey data) (Table 2). In terms of format, tabular data is primarily in .xlsx or .docx format or via AIRTABLE. Text data is primarily in .docx or .pdf format. Presentation data is primarily in .pptx format. Recording data is primarily in .mp3 and .mp4 format. Literature review data will be compiled in tabular form on Zotero. SHARE IT data is generated in .xlsx and .pdf formats. Website data is primarily graphics, text and a html code bank.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Table 2 Data generated or re-used in relation to CULTIVATE objectives

Objectives	Data and Purpose of Data
<p>O1.1: To monitor project progress and ensure compliance with legal, contractual, reporting and financial requirements, including the submission of timely high-quality deliverables;</p> <p>O1.2: To establish and maintain good communication with the EC, within the consortium, and with the high-level AB;</p> <p>O1.3: To develop and implement an effective risk management strategy;</p> <p>O1.4: To develop and monitor plans for data management and the ethical conduct of research.</p>	<p>Summary of data to achieve WP1 Objectives Contact data for internal communications, project logs to monitor decisions, changes and risks, text data for update reports and meeting minutes, audio-visual and presentation data to support internal communications</p> <p>Processed data will inform the following public facing research outputs D1.2 DMP D1.3 Updated DMP D1.4 Post Project DMP</p>

<p>O2.1: Co-produce a multilingual European Dictionary of Food Sharing to enable accurate identification, categorisation and mapping of FSIs;</p> <p>O2.2: Identify 100 diverse EU MS/AC UPU locations for mapping, tracking and monitoring of FSIs;</p> <p>O2.3: Develop, test and validate an automated system – <i>SHARECITY200</i> - for mapping, categorising, tracking and monitoring FSIs across 100 selected UPU locations.</p>	<p>Summary of data to achieve WP2 Objectives Literature review of the state of the art on ethical translation of terminology; Survey data to gather translation feedback from partners. Response data from citizen science crowd sourcing campaign on translating food sharing terms. Audio visual and presentation data to communicate translation processes to translators. Workshop data on translations; Machine generated web scraping data for food sharing activities in 100 cities in Europe; Field notes, observations and quantitative data about food sharing activities in Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan; Interview data with stakeholders; Re-use of SHARECITY100 data from SHARECITY</p> <p>Processed data will inform the following public facing research outputs D2.1 Manual for categorising FSIs, including the European Food Sharing Dictionary D2.2 Briefing note or Hub UPU FSI landscape</p>
<p>O3.1: Identify costs, investments, challenges, drivers, and success factors required to establish and maintain UPU FSIs;</p> <p>O3.2: Identify and assess the social, economic, and environmental impacts of UPU FSIs to establish the sustainability credentials of their activities;</p> <p>O3.3: Develop, test and validate a holistic multicriteria framework – the <i>Food Sharing Calculator</i> – for establishing the benefits and investments needed to support sustainable food sharing.</p>	<p>Summary of data to achieve WP3 objectives Qualitative data from secondary sources, (e.g., summaries of reviewed academic and grey literature), and from primary sources (e.g., interview notes and transcripts, observation notes, quotes by workshop participants) from mobile research labs in Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan; ; Quantitative and qualitative data from conducting SHARE IT SIA assessments on FSIs in Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan Re-use of SHARE IT toolkit and data from SHARECITY</p> <p>Processed data will inform the following public facing research outputs D3.1 Briefing note on cumulative FSI impacts in Hubs D3.2 <i>Food Sharing Calculator</i> prototype</p>
<p>O4.1: Establish how different food sharing landscapes evolve with respect to multilevel governance, improving understanding of how policy and regulation affect UPU FSIs;</p> <p>O4.2: Co-produce knowledge on how to transform existing regulatory regimes, governance structures</p>	<p>Summary of data to achieve WP4 objectives Literature review data on state of the art of food sharing governance; Workshop data (observation notes, participant quotes, quantitative data) from food sharing labs in Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan; Interview data with stakeholders; Re-use of data</p>

<p>and habits, to prevent and reduce food waste and promote sustainable food sharing;</p> <p>O4.3: Formulate a dynamic and interactive <i>Menu of Good Governance</i> to support sustainable food sharing.</p>	<p>from SHARECITY's futuring and scenario based governance data</p> <p>Processed data will inform the following public facing research outputs</p> <p>D4.1 Policy Brief 1: Briefing note on models and impacts of food sharing governance</p> <p>D4.2 A guidebook on inclusive, participatory and resilient sustainable UPU food sharing scenario planning</p> <p>D4.3 <i>Menu of Good Governance</i> prototype</p>
<p>O5.1: Understand the evolution of social norms, cultures, and local conditions and their impact on citizen engagement in food sharing innovations - with particular attention to COVID-19 to identify mechanisms which help to remove barriers to engagement;</p> <p>O5.2: Identify, assess, test, refine, and validate novel and existing methods for citizen engagement in socially innovative food sharing that are responsive to these social norms, cultures, and local conditions;</p> <p>O5.3: Activate insights to create an open access, user-friendly <i>Library of Citizen Engagement</i> to enhance opportunities and overcome barriers for sustainable UPU food sharing.</p>	<p>Summary of data to achieve WP5 objectives</p> <p>Literature review data on state of the art of citizen engagement through serious games; Interview data with stakeholders; Workshop data from lab and kitchen pop ups and game co-design spaces</p> <p>Processed data will inform the following public facing research outputs</p> <p>D5.1 Three serious game prototypes</p> <p>D5.2 <i>Library of Citizen Engagement</i> prototype</p>
<p>O6.1: Create a strong <i>EU Sustainable Food Sharing CoP</i> through a <i>Food Sharing Amplification Programme</i> offering peer-to-peer learning between and beyond Hub and Spoke FSI partners;</p> <p>O6.2: Replicate CULTIVATE's social innovation and decision support tools (created in WP 2-5) with CoP members, scaling them out to Spoke locations;</p> <p>O6.3: Integrate the refined tools into the <i>Food Sharing Compass</i> – an interactive online tool co-developed with and for the five target groups of the urban food sharing transition.</p>	<p>Summary of data to achieve WP6 Objectives</p> <p>Audio-visual data of webinar series in year one, with associated text summary. Text and tabular data of innovation action plans for bootcamp participants. Internally managed contact data for participants of Amplification programme; Similar data to WP2-5 will be generated for replication activities in spoke locations (web scarping data, workshop data, interview data, SIA data, etc.)</p> <p>Processed data will inform the following public facing research outputs</p> <p>D6.2 Policy Brief 2: inclusive, participatory and resilient sustainable UPU food sharing scenario planning</p> <p>D6.3 Policy Brief 3: Using the Menu of Good Governance</p> <p>D6.4 European Food Sharing <i>Community of Practice</i></p>

	<i>D6.5 CULTIVATE Food Sharing Compass</i>
<p>O7.1: Raise awareness and understanding around food resilience challenges and new concepts of urban food sharing economy;</p> <p>O7.2: Disseminate actionable knowledge from the CULTIVATE results to multi-level policy makers, from local to EU level and beyond;</p> <p>O7.3: Develop a post-project exploitation plan to ensure sustainability of results beyond the project timeline;</p> <p>O7.4: Measure the effectiveness of the Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy through dedicated outreach and engagement KPIs.</p>	<p>Summary of data to achieve WP7 objectives Communications data will include social media content (text and graphics), website/navigation data (text, media, html code), standardised project template documents (word and presentations templates), photographs, personal data of subscribers generate through the individual registration on the website and data relating to the delivery of events, webinars. ICONS processes personal data (gathered through website subscription, events attendance, webinar registration, etc) to enable its dissemination activities.</p> <p>Processed data will inform the following public facing research outputs D7.4 Updated CULTIVATE CDE D7.5 CDE report and impact analysis D7.7 Batch 1: 6 EIP AGRI Practice Abstracts D7.8 Batch 2: 6 EIP AGRI Practice Abstracts</p>

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

It is difficult to quantify the size of data in this early stage in the project. A previous 5 year, similar research project generated 300GB of data. It is unlikely CULTIVATE data will exceed 1TB (1000 GB). Currently the CULTIVATE team has 1TB of secure cloud storage capacity through the Microsoft SharePoint licence, held by the Co-Ordinator's host institution (TCD).

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

CULTIVATE data will be generated from literature reviews, web scraping, workshops, interviews, surveys and meetings. Generated data will be in multiple formats including text, tabular, audio and visual media.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

- **Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs)** any group that grows food together, cooks and/or eats food together and/or redistributes surplus food
- **Policy makers** municipalities, regional governments, territorial agencies, associations representing interests of local governments; national/EU policy makers; international bodies
- **Food supply actors** producers, manufacturers, retailers, warehouses, waste management services, restaurant services
- **Researchers** multidisciplinary, academic and extra-academic researchers at EU/international level; universities, RTOs; socioeconomic and environmental experts

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- **Citizens** individuals living in a locality (with or without local citizenship or residency status) in EU MS/AC UPU areas

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

By using [Zenodo](#) as the public repository for CULTIVATE data, [Zenodo](#) will generate two DOIs; one to denote the specific version of your record and another to denote all of the versions of your record. For example, when this DMP is uploaded to the [project website](#) and its metadata logged in [Zenodo](#), there will be a DOI for this version, and a DOI that consolidates all three updated DMP versions.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Per Grant Agreement, compulsory metadata fields for all CULTIVATE data are: “publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe funding attribution; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant”.

CULTIVATE metadata will be stored indefinitely on [Zenodo](#). CULTIVATE will use the 15 Metadata fields and vocabulary derived from the “Dublin Core metadata” standard which aligns with OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives.

For spreadsheet data, metadata will be provided in tabular form in the first sheet. In text data, metadata will be provided in tabular form on the within the first 3 pages.

Table 3 Metadata fields to be used for CULTIVATE's shareable data and research outputs

Metadata Field	Source	Optional/ Compulsory
License and rights	Dublin Core metadata Grant Agreement	Compulsory (Grant Agreement stipulates it should be CC BY or CC 0)
Persistent Unique Identifier (URL, DOI, etc.)	Dublin Core metadata Grant Agreement	Compulsory
Publication Date	Dublin Core metadata Grant Agreement	Compulsory
Publisher	Dublin Core metadata	Compulsory

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	Grant Agreement	
Author	Dublin Core metadata Grant Agreement	Compulsory
Contributor(s)	Dublin Core metadata Grant Agreement	Compulsory
Grant information- project name, acronym, and number Horizon Europe Funding Attribution	Grant Agreement	Compulsory
Embargo details	Grant Agreement	Compulsory if applicable
Ethics and GDPR statement	N/A	Compulsory if applicable
Description	Dublin Core metadata Grant Agreement	Optional
Subject	Dublin Core metadata	Optional
Type of data	Dublin Core metadata	Optional
Format	Dublin Core metadata	Optional
Source of data	Dublin Core metadata	Optional
Language	Dublin Core metadata	Optional
Location (virtual and/or physical)	Dublin Core metadata	Optional
Guidelines for using the data (e.g. software required)	N/A	Optional (Compulsory if propriety (non-open) software required to use the data)
Keywords	N/A	Optional

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Metadata will include a field for keywords and certain consistent keywords will be applied to all shared data to maximise findability.

Within [Zenodo](#), a unique community called 'CULTIVATE Project' will be created and used for all project records to consolidate the projects records in [Zenodo](#). All CULTIVATE records will also be part of the 'European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE)' community.

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Pre-existing [Zenodo](#) keywords that will be used include “Horizon Europe”; “Food System” and “Food Sharing”. Additional relevant keywords will be used at a WP level (e.g. “serious games” for WP5 datasets or “Machine Learning” for WP2 data).

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

[Zenodo](#) supports harvesting of content via the OAI-PMH protocol. All data archived in Zenodo and its accompanying metadata will be available for harvesting.

[Miksa et al \(2019\)](#) provides 10 principles for maximising machine actionability of data sharing. Ensuring metadata is machine actionable is one way to maximise it being harvested and indexed. Within CULTIVATE these are applied to metadata by using controlled vocabulary (metadata fields, keywords, etc), making data and metadata publicly available, applying SEO considerations to all research outputs, keeping the DMP as a live, versioned document, use of persistent unique identifiers, and applying ongoing monitoring and evaluation

A consistent naming convention will be applied across all CULTIVATE shared data and a table of rich descriptive metadata (Table 2). Public facing shareable data will follow a four staged naming convention of: CULTIVATE.filename.date.version. An official project list of keywords will also be used to consolidate research outputs and public facing data under consistent themes. All food sharing compass tools will be fully open access with CC BY usage licences. WP Leaders will consult with the CDE lead, ICONS, on how to ensure Search Engine Optimisation will be maximised for all their research outputs, as they are published and disseminated.

3.2. Making data accessible

3.2.1. Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Shareable data and metadata for restricted access data and research outputs will be deposited in OpenAIRE’s [Zenodo](#) repository. In addition, relevant partners can choose to deposit their data in their local institutional repositories (Appendix 1)

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Within [Zenodo](#), a unique community called ‘CULTIVATE Project’ will be created and used for all project records to consolidate the projects records in [Zenodo](#). All CULTIVATE records will also be part of the ‘European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE)’ community.

Pre-existing [Zenodo](#) keywords that will be used include “Horizon Europe”; “Food System” and “Food Sharing”. Additional relevant keywords will be used at a WP level (e.g. “serious games” for WP5 datasets or “Machine Learning” for WP2 data).

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve

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the identifier to a digital object?

[Zenodo](#) will generate two DOIs; one to denote the specific version of your record and another to denote all of the versions of your record. For example, when this DMP is uploaded to the [project website](#) and its metadata logged in [Zenodo](#), there will be a DOI for this version, and a DOI that consolidates all three updated DMP versions.

3.2.2. Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

There are five categories of CULTIVATE's data being discussed in the DMP:

- **Non-shareable data**- will not be made available. The eligible criteria are Privacy; Intellectual Property and/ or jeopardising the project's main objectives. These include the project deliverables with a 'SEN' status.
- **Metadata**- data describing restricted access data, shareable data and research outputs, according to the standardised fields specified in Table 2. Metadata will be deposited on the [Zenodo](#) repository, under a CC0 usage license, and remain available for at least five years after the project ends.
- **Restricted access data**- raw data generated by research and innovation activities. These data will not be deposited on [Zenodo](#), and needs to be requested by contacting the data author. Metadata on [Zenodo](#) for these data will include details on how to request the data from the data author
- **Shareable data**: raw data generated by research and innovation activities that will be made openly available on [Zenodo](#), and additional appropriate repositories, according to FAIR principles. Sharing of shareable data may be subject to embargos relating to publication of research outputs. All shareable data will be licensed as Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY).
- **Research outputs**: data generated by research and innovation activities that has undergone processing, analysis, critical review and presented in an accessible open access format designed for target groups. Research outputs include project deliverables with a 'PU' status, reports, policy briefs, interactive online tools, AIRTABLE spreadsheets, peer reviewed literature, video presentations, summary graphics, public project deliverables and other accessible forms of documents and media. All research outputs created by CULTIVATE will be made freely available on the [project website](#) and shared on relevant platforms such as MUFPP and GAIN's Food Action Cities platform and the EU Food Loss and Food Waste resources platform. In addition to publication on the [project website](#), PU project deliverables will be available on CORDIS and metadata for all research outputs will be deposited on [Zenodo](#). All research outputs will be licensed for free use, under a Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY).

Per Grant Agreement, CULTIVATE partners will “disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.”

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Embargos: Delaying dissemination of **shareable data** may apply if the **research output** is an academic peer reviewed article, or subject to intellectual property/ patent protection. The consortium will communicate internally to ensure publishing data does not compromise its future outputs as a research article, or its protection as intellectual property if applicable. Per grant agreement, “all partners must give at least 15 days advance notice to the consortium, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.” The time to publish will vary by output e.g. length of review or commercialisation processes.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

CULTIVATE’s research outputs and shareable data will be open access under Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY). Open research outputs will be available on the [project website](#), with metadata signposting its location on the [Zenodo](#) repository. Shareable data will be available as open access on the [Zenodo](#) repository. Metadata for restricted access data will be available as open access on the [Zenodo](#) repository, including instructions for requesting access from the data author. CULTIVATE will specifically ensure open access of all peer-reviewed publications, and their associated shareable data. Either Green or Gold Open access policy will be followed. A limited budget for open access fees are included in the budget.

The [project website](#), [Zenodo](#) repository and relevant institutional repositories all use Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) whereby users can access the data by clicking a link that loads the data in their browser or allows them to download the data. CULTIVATE research outputs and shareable data will be uploaded in a usable format. Efforts will be made to reduce the need for specific propriety software to access or use the data (e.g. Microsoft Office). As much as feasible, alternative open file types will be offered; .csv .txt, .jpeg, on the repositories

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

In some cases, data authors may have justification for their data that contributes towards a CULTIVATE research output to be restricted access data, instead of shareable data. If sensitive data arises, the data author will provide a justification in the metadata description for why this data is restricted. Access to the data will be provided via email contact with the data author. If a data author chooses restricted access for their data, they commit to maintaining the data and responding to email data requests for up to 5 years after the project end.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

The identity of the person accessing the data will only be ascertained and recorded if there is a justifiable reason and in compliance with GDPR legislation. If restricted access data has a justified reason to record the person accessing the data, it is the responsibility of the data author to record and store this information using informed consent and secure storage facilities.

The impact and effectiveness of applying FAIR principles to CULTIVATE data will be assessed within [Zenodo](#) by monitoring how many times **shareable data** and **metadata** are viewed and downloaded.

The [project website](#) analytics will be used to monitor how many times **research outputs** are viewed and downloaded.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

It is expected that the majority of CULTIVATE data will be open access as either shareable data or research outputs. It is not necessary to have a data access committee. Requests by data authors to keep data as restricted access will be discussed on a case-by-case basis under the 'data management' standing agenda item during quarterly Executive Board meetings.

3.2.3. Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

All metadata will be openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement, on the [Zenodo](#) repository. For restricted access data, the metadata will contain contact details for the data author. For shareable data, the metadata will have linked downloadable files in open formats of the datasets, for research outputs metadata will include links to the location of the research output on the [project website](#).

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Shareable data and research outputs will remain available on [Zenodo](#) and the [project website](#) respectively for at least 5 years after the project. Metadata for restricted access data, shareable data and research outputs will remain available on [Zenodo](#) indefinitely after the project

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

If open format versions of shareable data are not possible, the metadata field of 'Guidelines for using the data (e.g. software required)' will be completed by the data author to maximise access and usability of the data.

3.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

The 15 Metadata categories from the “Dublin Core Metadata” standard will be applied to all restricted access data, shareable data and research outputs from CULTIVATE (Table 2). The “Dublin Core metadata” standard which aligns with OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives.

Data exchange and re-use will also be maximised by depositing metadata and shareable data on the [Zenodo](#) repository, with unique DOIs.

Re-use within and across disciplines will be maximised through the use of standard pre-existing “communities” and “keywords” on [Zenodo](#), as well as creating a new searchable [Zenodo](#) community called “CULTIVATE project”. All CULTIVATE’s metadata and shareable data will use the pre-existing [Zenodo](#) keywords of “Horizon Europe”; “Food System” and “Food Sharing”.

Shareable data will be provided in accessible, shared, and open formats to maximise re-usability. Datasets in .xlsx and .docx files will have alternative .csv and .text formats deposited on the repository.

Research outputs include open access interactive online tools, collated under the ‘food sharing compass’ that will be co-designed with end users to maximise usability. Metadata for these tools and the shareable data informing the development of these tools will be deposited on [Zenodo](#).

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

All CULTIVATE metadata (for restricted access data and research outputs on the [project website](#)) and shareable data on [Zenodo](#) will be grouped under a project specific term “CULTIVATE project” to enable stakeholders aware of the project to search [Zenodo](#) and view all project data in one space. However, to map this unique term onto standard terms, all data on [Zenodo](#) will also be mapped under the pre-existing searchable community of “European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE)” and pre-existing searchable keywords of “Horizon Europe”; “Food System” and “Food Sharing”.

Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

If future research outputs draw from previously published CULTIVATE data (restricted access data, shareable data) the relevant citation on [Zenodo](#) (including its unique DOI) will be used as a qualified reference.

If future research outputs draw from CULTIVATE research outputs such as journal articles, reports or policy briefs, a qualified citation to the publication will be applied.

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

The key pieces of re-used data from previous research are the SHARECITY100 dataset, and the SHARE IT toolkit. Both these data have qualified references as follows:

- Davies, A.R. et al. (2016) SHARECITY100 Database, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland. Retrieved from: <https://sharecity.ie/research/sharecity100-database/>
- Davies, A.R., Franck, V. and Mackenzie, S.G. (2020) SHARE IT toolkit, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland. Retrieved from: <https://shareit.sharecity.ie/>

3.4. Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Data exchange and re-use within the consortium will be a priority as data generated by work could have multiple re-uses and applications across CULTIVATE. Details of methods for data analysis will be included in all research outputs (e.g. peer reviewed publications) and explanations of how data was generated and analysed to inform the KER - the Food Sharing Compass - will be provided in appropriate text files on [Zenodo](#).

To maximise data re-use beyond CULTIVATE we will proactively disseminate all project outputs using the CDE strategy developed by ICONS, engage directly with other relevant research projects and include representatives from all stakeholder groups in advisory groups. Using CC licences where feasible will facilitate re-use of tools and data. Where possible CULTIVATE research data will be provided, upon request to the contact authors, in compatible file formats for standard research tools such as Microsoft Office, R, NVIVO.

Data deposited on [Zenodo](#) will have rich descriptive meta data (Table 2) and, when possible, open file formats will be used and additional ReadMe files provided.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

CULTIVATE metadata, shareable data and research outputs will be made freely available in the public domain. To maximise access and re-use, all metadata (for restricted access data, shareable data and research outputs) will be made available under a CC 0 licence, on [Zenodo](#). All shareable data will be licensed as Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY or CC BY-NC-SA), on [Zenodo](#). All research outputs will be licensed as Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY or CC BY-NC-SA), on the [project website](#).

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Under a CC BY licence, shareable data and research outputs will be freely available for use of third parties. Metadata will be applied to each shareable data and research output file, to maximise findability and accessibility in the public domain by both human and machine based third parties. These data will be available for a minimum of 5 years after the end of the project

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Metadata field, “source of data”, ensures documentation of data provenance (Table 2). If any CULTIVATE data draw from pre-published CULTIVATE data, the data author will use appropriate qualified references and include the [Zenodo](#) DOI.

[Zenodo](#) DOIs provide provisions for version control, to ensure documentation of data provenance. There will be one DOI for the piece of data, and a DOI for each version of that data. For example, there will be a DOI that applies to all three versions of this data management plan, and a separate DOI that applies uniquely to this version. This creates a documented link between multiple versions of CULTIVATE’s data. This will be particularly applicable and important for linking the prototype food sharing compass tools developed in hub cities, and the final tools refined in the spoke locations and integrated into the food sharing compass.

A consistent naming convention will be applied across all CULTIVATE shared data. Public facing shareable data will follow a four staged naming convention of: *CULTIVATE.filename.date.version*. The date.version component of file names will support documentation of data provenance.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

All research outputs are subject to a quality control review by a member of the Executive Board. Authors of research outputs need to submit deliverables to the quality control reviewer at least 1 month in advance of submitting the deliverable for dissemination.

Data management will be a standing agenda item in all quarterly Executive Board meetings. All WP leaders will reflect on their data management practices and actions and submit a status of their data management according to the RAG system (red, amber, green) at each Executive Board meeting. Amber issues relating to data management will be resolved with the support of the Coordinator and Executive Board. Red issues relating to data management will be resolved in collaboration with the European Commission Project Officer.

The project manager has responsibility to review and maintain the quality of metadata being deposited in [Zenodo](#), ensuring compliance with the quality control standards of the Dublin Core Metadata standard and Grant Agreement specifications, as outlined in Table 2.

4. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

CULTIVATE will consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated throughout their projects as follows:

Digital code banks

CULTIVATE will deliver a comprehensive variety of open access virtual tools and toolkits to enable innovation within urban food systems. Several of these tools will have back-end code banks to deliver accessible front facing tools for the target user. Examples of research outputs that will have code banks include the [project website](#), the food sharing compass, SHARECITY200, SHARE IT and virtual serious games. While the tools themselves are '**research outputs**' and will be fully available under CC BY usage licence, the code banks will be '**non-shareable data**'. This is because sharing of the code bank exposes the tools to data security risks, including hacking. Additionally, the code bank may be subject to patent and intellectual property rights of either the CULTIVATE partner and/or the sub-contracted developer.

Innovation action protocols

Being an Innovation Action, CULTIVATE will apply novel protocols to achieve its objectives. These protocols are created and owned by the CULTIVATE partners. Open access to these protocols as '**shareable data**' could compromise the project objectives and/or the intellectual property status of these protocols. Therefore, protocols will be available as '**restricted access data**'. Protocol creators have discretion on the extent to which they share their innovative protocols. Partners will create an open access metadata record for each protocol, on [Zenodo](#), to indicate to the public that these protocols exist and how to learn more through contact with the protocol creators. Examples of innovative protocols belonging to the CULTIVATE partners include:

- Mobile Research Lab protocol tailored for a food sharing context by ULUND.
- Food Sharing Lab protocol tailored for policy makers and a food sharing context by UB
- Game co-design workshop protocol tailored for developing food sharing themed games with citizens by WUR
- Lab and Kitchen protocol for engaging citizens with food sharing themed discussions by Cas

Lab and Kitchen equipment

CULTIVATE partner Cas will develop pop up interventions in the project and will acquire physical kitchen facilities in Hub and Spoke locations. Cas will maximise re-use of equipment between its Lab and Kitchen pop ups in Hub and Spoke cities. When the equipment is no longer needed for CULTIVATE objectives, Lab and Kitchen will investigate the best options to make these physical resources available to stakeholders in the local area.

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Community hub building

CULTIVATE will rent a building in one of its hub locations, Utrecht, for 10 months. This is to facilitate its citizen science objectives and outputs, particularly in WP5. In line with FAIR principles and open access ethos, where feasible and permitted under insurance and other regulations locally, this building and CULTIVATE outputs will be available for other community engagement and enhancement activities. Access and use of this physical space will be managed by CULTIVATE partner, Utr.

5. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

How will these be covered?

Direct costs for making CULTIVATE data FAIR include:

- Open access fees for peer reviewed journal articles. All academic partners have budget allocated for this.
- Microsoft SharePoint licence for internal storage data security. This cost is covered through the 'institutional capacity' of the coordinating institution, TCD. TCD provides the full suite of Microsoft Teams, SharePoint and other features to CULTIVATE partners. This includes two factor authentication to access CULTIVATE's internal data and other best practice data security provisions for the internal cloud storage and sharing of CULTIVATE data. This is also where '**non-shareable data**' will be stored securely among the CULTIVATE partners.
- Secure storage of **research outputs** on the [project website](#) for five years after the project has direct security costs of an active SSL cert and storage costs of website hosting on a server. The WP7 lead, ICONS, has dedicated budget to cover these costs
- Secure storage of **metadata** and **shareable data** on [Zenodo](#) is provided for free by OpenAIRE

Indirect costs for making CULTIVATE data FAIR are the working hours of CULTIVATE staff to manage filing system, apply naming conventions and generate metadata are included in partners' person months in WP1 and each WP leads' person months for their WP's data management.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The Project Manager, with WP leads (Executive Board), will be responsible for ensuring data collection, storage, utilisation, and publication is compliant with regulations and best practice for ethics, storage and GDPR.

The Project Manager is responsible for writing the DMP (3 versions) and supporting its implementation. The project manager is responsible for uploading **metadata** and **shareable data** to [Zenodo](#), in collaboration with the relevant data authors. The project manager is also responsible for managing access by consortium partners to the internal Microsoft team, where **non-shareable data** is securely stored.

The Coordinator, with the support of the Project Manager, is responsible for monitoring the implementation of the DMP among WP leaders. This will be achieved through quarterly status updates from the WP leads and keeping 'data management' as a standing agenda item on the Executive Board meeting agendas.

ICONS, with the support of the Project Manager and data author, will be responsible for uploading **research outputs** to the [project website](#) and ensuring an associated metadata entry is deposited in [Zenodo](#)

WP Leads will be responsible for managing the data within their work package, using the DMP as a guiding resource and in proactively collaborating with the Project Manager, Coordinator and partner ICONS to ensure timely deposits of relevant data on [Zenodo](#) and the [project website](#). WP leads will decide contact details for any **restricted access data** within their WP.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Full details and arrangements for all CULTIVATE data post project will be decided by the Executive Board in the final year of the project and detailed in the “D1.4: post project data management plan”, due in December 2026. Provisionally, the following arrangements are planned for ensuring long term preservation:

- The Coordinator, will keep the internal Microsoft SharePoint storage of '**non-shareable**' data active for five years after the project end
- The institution of the data author will ensure valid, live contact details are provided, via metadata details on [Zenodo](#), for the public to request restricted access data for up to five years after the project ends
- Coordinator will keep the open access **shareable data** and **metadata** available on [Zenodo](#) for five years after the project end
- WP 7 Lead, ICONS, have budget to maintain the [project website](#) as a live repository of open access **research outputs** and outputs for five years after the project end.

6. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Data recovery

Each CULTIVATE staff member, in consultation with their line manager, is responsible for ensuring regular back-up of the CULTIVATE data being stored on their equipment or internal servers. All CULTIVATE staff have been given the option to use TCD's SharePoint cloud, through TCD's institutional Office 365 licence. There is a SharePoint folder available for each WP and task in CULTIVATE.

The Coordinator, TCD, ensures all data is backed up daily through live syncing between staff laptops and the TCD SharePoints. Using live syncing as a back-up mechanism is the recommended approach to all CULTIVATE staff. However, back up on a monthly schedule to a cloud or external hard drive device is also acceptable, if that is the partner's organisation's policy.

Secure storage

All CULTIVATE staff members should have password protection and updated anti-virus software on their work laptops.

All internal **non-shareable data** is managed through the TCD license with Office 365 (Microsoft Teams, SharePoint, OneDrive). A designated SharePoint for the whole consortium, and an exclusive private SharePoint for the executive board's sensitive data, has been provided. SharePoint requires two factor authentication from CULTIVATE staff. The security of SharePoint has been fully reviewed and validated by TCD IT services as a secure private method to store and share internal data within CULTIVATE, in line with relevant legislation on data security. SharePoint security is also monitored on an ongoing basis by TCD IT services. The Coordinator and Project Manager will be alerted through staff notifications if any security issue arises. The Coordinator does not condone the use of free cloud services by CULTIVATE partners (e.g. free google drive, dropbox, etc.) as these cloud systems have not been appropriately vetted for compliance with the latest legislation requirements on GDPR and data security. ***Project data should not be stored on these servers.***

Hard copy documentation relating to CULTIVATE data (e.g. fieldwork handwritten notes, workshop materials, paper surveys) should be stored in locked offices and digitised as soon as possible for secure, digital storage.

If a recording device is used to generate audio, video or photograph data (e.g. of interviews), data should be transferred to staff laptops as soon as possible and the file deleted from the recording device.

Transfer of sensitive data

Sensitive data in CULTIVATE should only be shared through SharePoint. Within SharePoint, there is the option to password protect shared data if access should only be between a subset of partners.

Data authors are encouraged to use password protection on SharePoint files as appropriate. The Coordinator and Project Manager should be kept informed of all file passwords.

Contact data for CULTIVATE partners is maintained in .xlsx format in the WP1 folder on SharePoint. Permission for storage and use of partner contact information is given through the 'business data permission' of the consortium agreement.

Additional contact data and personal information may be justifiably collected and stored by WP5 partners, due to the citizen facing nature of their project objectives. In this case, WP5 partners should defer to WUR's leadership and institutional guidelines on the use and storage of personal data.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

- **Non-shareable data** and **restricted access data** will continue to be stored on a Microsoft SharePoint within TCD for up to five years after the project end.
- **Shareable data** and **metadata** will continue to be stored on [Zenodo](#) for up to five years after the project end
- **Research outputs** will be stored on the [project website](#) for up to five years after the project end

7. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

All CULTIVATE partners should comply with their own organisations policies and guidelines on ethics and GDPR.

CULTIVATE partners conducted an ethics self-assessment during proposal development, and as outlined in the grant agreement (p 142-143). Ethics in CULTIVATE is monitored at a WP level, through quarterly status update reports from WP leaders to the Executive Board. Ethics is a standing agenda item in all Executive Board meetings. TCD, as Coordinator, is an 'ethics mentor' for the project, to support WP leads and other partners in implementing best ethical practices throughout their CULTIVATE work. In addition to the ethics self-assessment, all WP leaders conducted a gender impact assessment of their workplan.

Key ethical dimensions of CULTIVATE activities are participation of volunteers (adults only), collection of personal data and the use of AI. Each WP leaders will ensure their work is reviewed and approved by its institutional ethics committee and ensure their staff avail of any institution provided training on research integrity. CULTIVATE partner DCU have expertise in AI and will ensure ethical best practices are adhered to.

The [project website](#) has [public facing privacy statement](#).

The ethical implications for data sharing are primarily in relation to personal data and are detailed in the following question below:

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Appropriate care will be taken throughout CULTIVATE to respect subjects' data rights. We will obtain informed consent before collecting data through interviews, surveys or focus groups and will communicate our research through plain language statements. A standardised informed consent form will be used as a template by all partners when conducting research with people. This template will include consent in relation to data sharing and long-term preservation.

There should not be personal data in any **shareable data** or **research outputs** of CULTIVATE. Data must be anonymised to the extent that no individual person can be identified before these data are deposited on [Zenodo](#) or the [project website](#) respectively.

If any personal data is included in **restricted access data**, the GDPR field of the metadata must be completed, and the data author must exercise full compliance with GDPR in how long they store, and to what extent they share, this data.

If personal data is included in **non-shareable data**, there must be a GDPR note at the beginning of the data file indicating the consent and length of time this data can be justifiably stored on the internal SharePoint.

8. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?

Other data protection guidelines

All partners should comply with their organisational level GDPR and data protection policies in addition to the guidelines in this DMP. Particularly relevant other policies are the organisation level policies of the WP leads, which will have a downstream impact on all tasks within the WP. These are listed here

- [TCD data protection policy](#)
- [ULUND data protection policy](#)
- [UB data protection policy](#)
- [WUR data protection policy](#)
- [ICLEI data protection policy](#)
- [ICONS data protection policy](#)

Other ethics guidelines

A sub-set of CULTIVATE partners have formal ethical review procedures within their organisation. These organisational level procedures and policies should be applied in addition to compliance with this DMP and the Ethics-Self-Assessment commitments in the Grant Agreement.

- [TCD ethics guidelines](#)
- [ULUND ethics guidelines](#)
- [UB ethics guidelines](#)
- [WUR ethics guidelines](#)
- [ICLEI ethics guidelines](#)
- [ICONS ethics guidelines](#)

Other repositories

A sub-set of CULTIVATE partners have institutional repositories. If a CULTIVATE staff member from one of these partners is a data author, they can optionally deposit **shareable data** or **research outputs** in their local repository, **in addition to (but not instead of)** [Zenodo](#) / the [project website](#). These repositories have their own metadata standards, storage procedures and security provisions that may differ from the specific guidelines in this DMP.

Relevant additional institutional repositories include:

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- TCD repository - [TARA](#)
- ULUND repository- [Lund University Publications \(LUP\)](#)
- UB repository- [Dipòsit Digital de la Universitat de Barcelona](#)
- ICLEI repository- [ICLIE e-Library](#)

Additional National legislation

In addition to compliance with [EU law on data management](#), partners are subject to their additional national legislation of their EU member state. Relevant national legislation impacting CULTIVATE partners include:

- [Ireland data protection laws](#)
- [The Netherlands data protection laws](#)
- [Italy data protection laws](#)
- [Spain data protection laws](#)
- [Portugal data protection laws](#)
- [Germany data protection laws](#)
- [Czechia data protection laws](#)
- [Sweden data protection laws](#)

One associated partner, BHFP, is not located in an EU member state. Their work will still comply with the guidelines of this DMP, in addition to their national legislation:

- [UK data protection laws](#)

